

INTERNATIONAL
ASTRONOMICAL
UNION | OFFICE OF
ASTRONOMY FOR
DEVELOPMENT

ANNUAL REPORT

1 APRIL 2022 - 31 MARCH 2023

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

The content in this booklet is based on OAD project reports, quarterly reports, press releases, and published articles.

ACTIVITY IMAGES

Courtesy of the OAD projects

SECTOR HEADER PAGES

<https://www.nasa.gov/nasa-brand-center/images-and-media/>

COVER IMAGE

LoganArt on Pixaby.com

DESIGN

www.lithotech.co.za

OAD TEAM MEETS PRESIDENT OF SOUTH AFRICA AND MINISTERS

The OAD team had the privilege of meeting the President of South Africa, Cyril Ramaphosa, Minister of Higher Education, Science, Innovation, Dr Blade Nzimande, Minister of International Relations and Cooperation, Dr Naledi Pandor, officials from the Department of Science and Innovation, and other dignitaries at the 2022 World Science Forum.

The forum is a meeting to foster and maintain a dialogue between the scientific community, society, policy-makers, and industry. It emphasises the significance, relevance, and responsibilities of science on a global scale. It was held for the first time in Africa from 6-9 December 2022 in Cape Town, South Africa.

The OAD and the African Astronomical Society (AfAS) organised a side event on 'Advancing Africa's Astronomy Agenda'. It highlighted how various activities on the continent enable the advancement of astronomy in Africa and plans to ensure that Africa becomes one of the world's leaders in the field. OAD Director Kevin Govender presented several talks at the Forum, including a lightning talk at the International Science Council's Global Knowledge Dialogue, the special SKA breakfast, and the closing ceremony.

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
<https://www.astro4dev.org/oad-team-meets-president-of-south-africa/>

IAU GENERAL ASSEMBLY 2022

The most significant highlight of the year was the IAU General Assembly. Initially scheduled for 2021, the meeting was postponed due to the global pandemic and organised in hybrid format in August 2022. Several members of the OAD team and representatives from almost all regional offices were in attendance. The OAD's presence included an exhibition space along with other IAU Offices, an institutional meeting with 5 sessions of 90 minutes each (the last session was shared with the other IAU Offices), mini-workshops on flagship projects, and numerous side meetings with Divisions, regions and other stakeholders. It was an opportunity to present the work of the OAD and engage directly with regional offices and other stakeholders on flagship projects. Several communications resources were produced and disseminated at the IAU GA, which are also available electronically, such as the OAD Annual Report.

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
<https://www.astro4dev.org/oad-at-the-xxxi-iau-general-assembly/>

IMPACT OF 2022 PROJECTS

In 2022, the OAD funded 17 projects run by multidisciplinary teams that addressed local and global challenges through astronomy-related innovations. In early 2023, these projects presented the results of their activities in the past year, also sharing their achievements and challenges.

LIST OF PROJECTS FUNDED, IN ALPHABETICAL ORDER:

- 1 A Virtual Community Mentorship Program for Development in Colombia
- 2 Acornhoek Physics Summer School - South Africa
- 3 Astro3dbol - Archeoastronomy Teaching Kit in Bolivia
- 4 Astrolab 2022 - Africa
- 5 Astronomy for Community Empowerment in Nepal
- 6 Astronomy in Ghana
- 7 Astronomy Training Outreach for Preschool Teachers in Malaysia Through Service-Learning Approach
- 8 Astro-Tourism Development in Tanzania
- 9 Astro-Tourism with Nomadic Herder in Forest Area of Mongolia
- 10 Beyond The Beach: Foundations for Caribbean Astro - Tourism
- 11 Bringing Radio Astronomy to Classrooms with Affordable Radio Telescopes - Nigeria
- 12 Cenca Bridge - Central America and Caribbean
- 13 Cosmoamautas: Virtual Teacher Training in Vulnerable Regions in Peru
- 14 Education For All: Promoting Education In Internally Displaced Communities in Burkina Faso
- 15 Guide Training Workshop for Tribal Students - India
- 16 Mobile Astronomy Village - Benin
- 17 Scigirls - Empowering Girls in Science Through Astronomy - Ethiopia

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
Short video presentations from projects are available on the website
<https://www.astro4dev.org/projects-create-impact-across-the-world/>

INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF BASIC SCIENCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The International Year of Basic Sciences for Sustainable Development (IYBSSD) recognises that basic sciences are vital to attain sustainable development and to improve the quality of life for people all over the world. IYBSSD is organised by UNESCO, in collaboration with its global partners including the IAU, from July 2022 to July 2023. The OAD, serving as an example of basic sciences driving development, contributed to the organisation of IYBSSD.

A 24 hour, global livestream in June 2023 shared how scientific results, as well as ways of doing science, already contribute to building a better world for all.

NO POVERTY . ZERO HUNGER . GOOD HEALTH AND WELL BEING . QUALITY EDUCATION . GENDER EQUALITY . CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION . AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY . *Sustainable* DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH . *Development Goals* INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE . REDUCED INEQUALITIES . SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES . RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION . CLIMATE ACTION . LIFE BELOW WATER . PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS . PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
<https://www.iybssd2022.org/en/home/>

PUBLICATIONS

ASTRONOMY FOR DEVELOPMENT: CASE STUDIES

The OAD was established with the conviction that scientists, including astronomers, have much to offer in building an inclusive, sustainable world for all.

Since 2011, the OAD has funded and coordinated over 200 projects that use astronomy as a tool to address challenges in communities and fulfil some of these Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). More than 1.2 Million Euros has been granted to 217 projects globally. These projects have reached at least 2 million people in 100+ countries, impacting 11 of the 17 SDGs. Our case studies document the impact of selected projects. These projects encompass astronomy education, cultural astronomy, mental health, capacity building, and resource development, all with the goal of creating a positive impact. OAD Fellows, Dana Ficut-Vicas and Maria Alejandra Diaz, interviewed these OAD projects to understand how they are changing their communities and serving as examples of science promoting sustainable development.

Rediscovering Identity through Astronomy, Chile

Astronomy for students through interactive app & game, Bangladesh

Astronomy for Mental Health

Big Data Hackathons

Video Astronomy Lessons for School Children, Pakistan

OruMbya: Astronomy as a Fuel of Life, Brazil

ASTRONOMY FOR MENTAL HEALTH GUIDELINES

OAD Fellow Dominic Vertue and past Fellow Sandra Benitez published an article in the CAP Journal on guidelines for applying astronomy to benefit mental well-being.

Astronomy, with its vast array of tools and resources, can greatly benefit society. One area in need of new approaches and interventions is mental health and well-being. Diminished mental health can have a profound effect on society, from financial to loss of human potential. The OAD is exploring how astronomy can play a role in improving mental health and well-being. As part of its project on astronomy for mental health, the OAD is creating and publishing resources for astronomers, educators, science communicators, and others who may benefit from using astronomy in their activities.

One of the key resources being developed is the Astronomy for Mental Health Guidelines. This open-access document provides practical steps, tools, resources, and examples for planning, adapting or reviewing programmes or interventions targeting mental health and well-being. This article provides the background and context to the problem of mental health, motivations for using astronomy such as the shortfall in global mental healthcare services, a brief summary of the Guidelines and access to the Guidelines online.

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
<https://www.astro4dev.org/article-in-the-cap-journal-astronomy-for-mental-health-guidelines/>

Another article was published in the Mental Health Matters magazine on the "INTERSECTION BETWEEN ASTRONOMY AND MENTAL HEALTH".

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
<https://www.astro4dev.org/mental-health-matters-magazine-intersection-between-astronomy-and-mental-health/>

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
<https://www.astro4dev.org/astronomy-for-development-case-studies/>

PROJECTS

ANNUAL CALL FOR PROPOSALS

The 2022 call for proposals received 89 proposals at Stage 1, of which 41 proposals were invited to submit a full proposal. The review panel completed their evaluations in November 2022 and 17 projects were selected to receive funding in 2023 to use astronomy to further sustainable development. In addition, two multi-year projects, funded for 3 years from 2021-23, were approved for their second year of funding.

The new projects were welcomed in February 2023 during a virtual onboarding week. Projects span the globe, with activities taking place in Africa, Europe, Asia, North America, and South America. They will promote sustainable development using astronomy-related interventions. Examples include: a programme that will train young women teachers to promote science education in rural Botswana; development of an astrotourism academic curriculum in Tanzania; an after-school astronomy programme for families in a disadvantaged part of Northern Ireland; an inspirational astronomy-based programme for prisoners in Nigeria approaching their release dates; physics and astronomy training for young women in parts of Pakistan affected by conflict and more.

THE PROJECTS FUNDED, IN ALPHABETICAL ORDER, ARE:

UPDATES FROM PROJECTS

ASTRONOMY SCHOOL BUILDS CAPACITY IN AFRICA

In late 2022, the Pan-African School for Emerging Astronomers (PASEA) was organised in Zambia, the fifth in the series of schools that started in 2013 as West African International Summer School for Young Astronomers (WAISYA). It was jointly organised by the West African Regional Office of Astronomy for Development (WAROAD) and Southern African Regional Office of Astronomy for Development (SAROAD) in collaboration with astronomers and scientists from across the globe.

PASEA combined interactive lectures, problem-solving sessions, hands-on experience and inquiry-based activities to fulfil the human capacity needs of African students. Surveys showed that the program was very influential on the intending choice of career/study of over 90% of PASEA 2022 participants.

<https://www.astro4dev.org/astronomy-school-builds-capacity-in-africa/>

PRE-SCHOOL TEACHER TRAINING IN MALAYSIA

The project objectives were to develop an astronomy teaching and learning module for preschool teachers in Malaysia. Preschool teachers received training in fundamentals of astronomy and hands-on activities such as building sundials. The workshop resulted in an increase in the level of awareness, understanding and readiness of pre-school teachers to use astronomy.

<https://www.astro4dev.org/pre-school-teacher-training-in-malaysia/>

ASTRONOMY AND UPSKILLING AT A NIGERIAN PRISON

The Astro-prison project aimed to boost morale and create behavioural change among inmates at Nigerian prisons as well as provide practical job skills and improve literacy. The inmates were introduced to astronomy and the concept of the 'Pale Blue Dot' that emphasises togetherness and social cohesion. The team also conducted entrepreneurship training to improve employment prospects of inmates upon their release.

<https://www.astro4dev.org/astronomy-and-upskilling-at-a-nigerian-prison/>

PROJECT IMPROVES GIRLS ENROLLMENT IN RURAL KENYA

The EMEJA project addresses girls education issues in rural Kenya. The project used multiple interventions to tackle the issues – astronomy STEM workshops, mentorship, and scholarships – guided and supported by long-term student tracking and monitoring. It engaged 1074 schoolgirls in both primary and secondary schools, 16 secondary school teachers, numerous primary school teachers, and 10 tutors. As a result of the interventions, the number of girls selecting Physics in Year III shot up across the 4 schools. Science teachers have reported that there is a notable difference in the attitude of their female students towards sciences, particularly Physics. Teachers also reported an improvement in grades, particularly in Physics (improved from an average score of 37 to 45 and 49 to 52 in two schools). Schools were supported to purchase lab equipment and computers.

<https://www.astro4dev.org/project-improves-girls-enrollment-in-rural-kenya/>

DISADVANTAGED STUDENTS TRAINED AS ASTROGUIDES IN INDIA

AstroTribe is a science engagement and economic development project that provides astronomical knowledge and skills to tribal students, and trains them as astronomy guides, enabling them to earn income without interfering with their academic schedule. The project trained 16 astroguides, conducted 5 stargazing events that raised 30000 INR in revenue for the students, onboarded 12 international mentors and two resorts for astrotourism events. The project's long-term goal is to create a self-sustaining network for astrotourism in the region. To scale the project on a global level, an online networking platform is being developed to create a global network of AstroGuides, experts, resorts interested in Astrotourism as well as amateur astronomers.

<https://www.astro4dev.org/disadvantaged-students-trained-as-astroguides-in-india/>

GUIDE FOR CODE LEARNING WITH ASTRONOMICAL IDEAS

The project idea was to create a code learning program based on microbits and astronomical topics. Micro:bit is a pocket programmable device that allows children and young people to learn how to program in a simple, playful and creative way. The target audience were local students and teachers abroad in Mozambique and East Timor. Working with the teachers, a learning roadmap was created to teach coding based on astronomy ideas. The project chose a mission to Mars as the main activity, with several phases in order to be replicated in a simplified way through micro:bit coding and its sensors.

<https://www.astro4dev.org/guide-for-code-learning-with-astronomical-ideas/>

ASTRO3DBOL ARCHAEOASTRONOMY EDUCATIONAL KIT, BOLIVIA

The Astro3DBol project developed and distributed archaeoastronomy educational kits in the context of the Tiwanakota culture of Bolivia. The target audience were educators and those interested in astronomy and the pre-Inca cultures of Bolivia to help them develop a thematic class of Tiwanakota Archaeoastronomy. The training workshop focused on education, astronomy instruments, technical analysis of data, archeoastronomy and future educational projects.

<https://www.astro4dev.org/astro3dbol-archaeoastronomy-educational-kit-bolivia/>

BRAZILIAN PROJECT BRINGS TOGETHER ASTRONOMY, INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE, AND CULTURE

OruMbya (Orum, sky in Yorubá, and Mbya, a Brazilian Guarani ethnicity) is a pilot project to celebrate astronomy as a fuel of life. The stories of the stars of people from three different continents were shared through scientific-cultural activities that focused on the dissemination of knowledge, promotion of social inclusion and sustainable development. The hosts were the NGO Casa da Tia Ciata and the cultural centre “Remanescentes da Tia Ciata”, and the centenary Observatory of Valongo (OV), one of the oldest institutions of astronomy in Brazil. The project organised five public webinars, with the participation of astronomers, Indigenous people, chilombolas, activists from favelas and members of different countries, to promote an unbiased and equal virtual space of knowledge. Every event consisted of the organic combination of three experiences dedicated to – astronomy, African and Indigenous knowledge, and art or music, which were recorded and live broadcasted. Speakers and participants told stories and shared knowledge about culture and the sky, creating new multicultural collaborations and alliances. A course on Racialised Cosmologies: human rights, interculturality and ethnic-racial relations in science education was delivered online.

<https://www.astro4dev.org/brazilian-project-brings-together-astronomy-indigenous-knowledge-and-culture/>

FLAGSHIP 1

ASTRONOMY FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

This Flagship aims to use an astronomical facility, such as an observatory or planetarium, as a “hub” to stimulate various socio-economic benefits for the local community. Benefits could include job creation through astronomy related tourism; community skills development; educational programmes; stimulation of local innovation; alternative activities for youth in order to keep away from negative/harmful activities; and infrastructure development.

Samyukta Manikumar joined the team as an Astrotourism fellow, She is developing and consolidating resources relating to astrotourism in order to support the regions, related projects, and other potential champions of astrotourism around the world. She published the article ‘How to Start an Astrotourism Business’ in the Africa Science Stars special issue on astrotourism.

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
<https://astro4dev.org/astrotourism>

FLAGSHIP 2

ASTRONOMY FOR MENTAL HEALTH

This flagship aims to use the inspiring potential of astronomy to stimulate a sense of tolerance and common humanity. The beauty and scale of the universe can induce a 'universal' perspective which can influence how people interact with their fellow human beings and our planet.

Pilot activities were implemented in Armenia, Spain, and South Africa. In Armenia, an educational project was organised at a children's support center in collaboration with a psychologist. The team observed improvement in mental well-being, change of perception, an unusual level of tolerance and a sense of interpersonal values. In Spain, astronomy talks and a psychological survey were organised for elderly people. The psychological survey and the general motivation test showed a high level of satisfaction and a positive impact on self-esteem and emotions. In South Africa, a workshop was organised for the Cape Town Community Mental Health and Psychiatry Foundation to demonstrate the potential of astronomy for mental well-being.

Dominic Vertue joined the OAD as a Mental Health fellow. He led further activities with the South African Depression and Anxiety Group (SADAG), Community Health and Psychiatry Foundation, and workshops at the Iziko Planetarium to introduce astronomy to mental health care workers. He also published an article in a medical journal to attract the attention of and stimulate potential collaboration with those in the medical community as well as an article in the IAU CAP Journal.

The team launched public guidelines on 'Astronomy for Mental Health' to support others around the world in running similar interventions.

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
<https://www.astro4dev.org/astronomy-mental-health>

FLAGSHIP 3

ASTRONOMY KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS FOR DEVELOPMENT

This flagship focuses on the use of knowledge and skills used in astronomy to tackle development challenges.

This includes methods, techniques widely used in the field including data handling, data analysis, machine learning as well as the necessary compute facilities.

Together with DARA Big Data and partners, several hackathons were organised to expose students and young people to data science through astronomy. A hackathon at the University of Mauritius, one in Peru coordinated by the Andean Regional Office, and multiple hackathons in South Africa. The local partners in the project, the Inter University Institute for Data Intensive Astronomy, African Astronomical Society, BRICS Astronomy, and OAD are taking the activities forward under the banner of Hack4dev. All project resources are now consolidated on www.hack4dev.org.

FOLLOW THE QR CODE, OR VISIT:
www.hack4dev.org

MEETINGS & EVENTS

The OAD steering committee gathered for the annual meeting in January 2023. The meeting returned to in-person at the OAD office in Cape Town.

Kevin Govender and Vanessa McBride attended the American Astronomical Society (AAS) Meeting in Seattle, USA where they presented the OAD and IAU GA 2024.

Dominic Vertue presented the Astronomy for Mental Health Flagship at the African Astronomical Society Meeting. Several others from the OAD team also attended this meeting and the data science hackathon.

The OAD participated in a special session at the US-Africa Summit, organised by the African Astronomical Society and the African-European Radio Astronomy Platform (AERAP).

Sonal Asgotraa, Tawanda Chingozha and Nikhita Madhanpall presented a workshop virtually at the Communicating Astronomy with the Public conference. The workshop introduced development concepts to astronomy communicators.

Vanessa McBride attended the European Astronomical Society meeting in Valencia, Spain in June 2022, and was involved in the SOC of two key sessions: SS38 Africa-Europe collaborations: current status and the road to 2024; and SS37 Astronomy for Development.

REGIONAL OFFICES

ANDEAN ROAD

- The office organised a Big Data Hackathon at the National University of Engineering, Peru. It was the first hackathon of the Andean Region attended by 25 undergraduate and graduate students of sciences and engineering.
- The IV Workshop Astronomía en los Andes will be organised in October 2023 on “Engaged communities in development through Astrotourism”. The main goal is to promote high-quality, responsible and innovative tourism of stars in the Andean Region, especially in rural areas where it could become a real driving force for local economies.

ARAB ROAD/LOAD

- The office organised, with the Jordanian Astronomical Society (JAS), the Arab Union for Astronomy and Space Science (AUASS) and some other Jordanian & Arab institutions, several public lectures, seminars, and courses.
- A conference on the “Important Figures in the History of the Arab-Islamic Civilisation in Science and Geography” was organised with the cooperation of the Jordanian Society for the History of Science. 150 participants joined from several Arab countries.
- An INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON SPACE EXPLORATION: MOON and BEYOND organised in cooperation with Asian Pacific Space cooperation organization- (APSCO). Attended by more than 15 representatives from different countries as (China, Jordan, Iran , pakitan, Egypt , Libia , Bangladesh , Sultanate of Oman , Palestine , Turkey , USA,Thailand, Algeria, Syria).

CHINESE & EAST ASIAN ROAD/LOAD

- The office took part in the International workshop “Educational Psychology and Astronomy for Mental health” in Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia from 19-21, May 2022.
- The Innovative Astronomy Forum “Talking about Astronomy and People, Empowering Future Development” project published several videos on the contribution and significance of astronomy to human exploration as well as improvement in our life. It was organised by the Chinese Astronomical Society, Shanghai Astronomical Observatory, Chinese Academy of Sciences, East Asia Regional Office, and supporters.

EAST AFRICAN ROAD

- The East African Office convened a special session on the African Dark Sky and Astro-tourism Strategy at the annual African Astronomical Society conference in March.
- The office presented its activities to the Ugandan Parliament Science and Technology Standing Committee, which visited the Space Science and Geospatial Institute in Ethiopia in February 2023.
- The East African Office is actively involved in the preparation and co-organisation of the IAU386 Symposium on astrotourism and dark skies, the Africa Planetarium Workshop and Capacity building on dark sky and Astro-tourism. These events will take place from November 11-17, 2023, in Addis Ababa.

EUROPEAN ROAD

- The office coordinated visits of researchers from other Regions under the Erasmus+ Twinning programme.

NORTH AMERICAN ROAD

- With funding from the Heising-Simons Foundation, the office is funding 10 projects across North America under its Women and Girls in Astronomy Program (WGAP). The selected projects will address the underrepresentation of women and girls in astronomy from a variety of perspectives.

PORTUGUESE ROAD

- The PLOAD office created a common agenda of three days to celebrate every year through online and local activities in the PLOAD regions.
- PLOAD is organising an art exhibition on African, Afro-Brazilian and Indigenous cosmologies.

SOUTH EAST ASIAN ROAD

- An official visit was conducted to LAO PDR by the Regional Office, led by the Minister of Higher Education, Science, Research and Innovation. The visit included a courtesy call granted by the Prime Minister of LAO PDR and the planetarium and observatory being-built in Vientiane which is inspired by the South East Asian ROAD.
- The ITCA Colloquium workshop co-hosted by SEAROAD and Vietnam National Space Center (VNSC) titled "Astronomy and Space Technology for STEAM Education" took place in Da Nang, Vietnam from 23-25 September 2022.

SOUTH WEST & CENTRAL ASIAN ROAD

- The office was involved in the organisation of the 8th Byurakan Science Camp (8BSC) as well as the 8th Byurakan International Summer School.
- The School Astronomical Lectures program in 2022 and 2023 visited 60 Armenian schools.

SOUTHERN AFRICAN ROAD

- The Pan African School of Emerging Astronomers (PASEA) was run in Zambia in October 2022 with 36 participants, supported by the OAD.
- The BIUST-MPG African Astronomy School was held in Botswana from 26 June to 7 July 2023.

WEST AFRICAN ROAD

- The office collaborated with the North American ROAD on the SEA Survey project which provides students the opportunity to conduct remote observing with the 0.5-meter Stone Edge Observatory telescope.
- The WAROAD office organized the Women and Girls in Astronomy Workshop on 8 March 2022. Speakers at the occasion were: Prof Ewin van Dishoeck, Prof. Vanessa McBride, Dr. Margaret Ikape, and Chioma Okany.
- The office organized a one-day World Asteroid Day conference on 30 June 2022.

NORTH AMERICA

ANDEAN REGION

WEST AFRICA

SOUTHERN AFRICA

EAST AFRICA

PORTUGUESE LANGUAGE

EUROPE

ARAB WORLD AND ARABIC LANGUAGE

SOUTH WEST AND CENTRAL ASIA

SOUTH EAST ASIA

EAST ASIA AND CHINESE LANGUAGE

PARTNERSHIPS

PARTNERSHIPS

DEVELOPMENT OF AFRICA THROUGH RADIO ASTRONOMY (DARA)

is a joint UK - South Africa Newton funded project that uses radio astronomy training to develop high level technical skills in young graduates. The partnership is an implementation of the astronomy-for-development concept and involves collaboration at both strategy and project evaluation levels.

DEVELOPMENT IN AFRICA WITH RADIO ASTRONOMY (DARA) BIG DATA PROJECT

is funded by the United Kingdom Newton Fund via the Science and Technologies Facilities Council, and aims to develop big data skills using radio astronomy in SKA African partner countries. Through a partnership with DARA Big Data, the OAD collaborated on organising hackathons that expose students and young people to big data and machine learning in both astronomy and development-related contexts

AFRICAN ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY (AFAS)

The African Astronomical Society was established in 2011, and is the voice of professional astronomy on the African continent. The purpose of the partnership between the OAD and AfAS is to provide and maximise a network of astronomy practitioners on the African continent, to respond rapidly to special events and to work together to implement and safeguard the legacy of the first General Assembly of the International Astronomical Union to be held on the African continent in 2024.

INTERNATIONAL VIRTUAL OBSERVATORY ALLIANCE (IVOA)

The IVOA was formed in June 2002 and aims to facilitate international coordination and collaboration in tools, systems and organizational structures for astronomical archives. The IVOA now comprises 20 Virtual Observatory programmes from Argentina, Armenia, Australia, Brazil, Canada, Chile, China, Europe, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Italy, Japan, Russia, South Africa, Spain, Ukraine, the United Kingdom, and the United States and an inter-governmental organization (ESA). The purpose of the partnership is to bring together the complementary resources and expertise of the IVOA and the OAD to advance the application of astronomical data and/or technology use in different areas of society, most notably for education, development and public outreach.

INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF BASIC SCIENCES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (IYBSSD)

An agreement was reached with the IYBSSD to list all OAD Regional Offices as "IYBSSD Nodes". The IAU is one of the official partners for IYBSSD through an MOU between the IAU and the International Union of Pure and Applied Physics (who is the coordinating organisation).

INTER-UNIVERSITY CENTRE FOR ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS (IUCAA)

India is one of the leading research institutes in astronomy/astrophysics globally. IUCAA also has a well renowned program of public outreach and education (SciPop). Since our establishment, OAD and IUCAA have enjoyed close ties. This partnership paves way for specific collaborations in capacity development along education, development and outreach.

ROYAL ASTRONOMICAL SOCIETY (RAS)

UK encourages and promotes the study of astronomy, solar-system science, geophysics and closely related branches of science. The RAS and OAD have partnered to establish or nurture research, educational and/or development related collaborations between the UK and countries where astronomy research is not well established.

PEOPLE

OAD TEAM

KEVIN GOVENDER
Director

NUHAAH SOLOMON
Admin and Logistics

VANESSA MCBRIDE
Deputy Director

RAMASAMY VENUGOPAL
Operations

OAD FELLOWS

Dominic
Vertue

Tawanda
Chingozha

Sonal
Asgotraa

Nikhita
Madhanpall

Tanita
Ramburuth-Hurt

Armine
Patatanyan

Sandra
Benitez Herrera

Tom
Mutabazi

Dana
Ficut-Vicas

Maria
Alejandra Diaz

Samyukta
Manikumar

FINANCIAL REPORT

COMPLIANCE: The OAD operates within the financial systems and policies of the National Research Foundation (NRF), which comply with South African national legislation. Compliance of the OAD's financial transactions to the relevant policies is tested through annual audits of the OAD's host organisation, South African Astronomical Observatory, and NRF. The OAD financial year (April to March) is different as compared to the implementation of funded projects (calendar year), and long-term special projects or grants (which can be multi-year).

OPERATIONS: For the duration of the IAU-NRF agreement, the OAD receives an annual core income from the DSI/NRF and the IAU, all administered through the NRF. Since the renewed IAU-NRF agreement in 2015, the DSI/NRF provides R1,500,000 per year with an annual inflationary increase of 6%, plus the salary and associated costs of a full time OAD astronomer (now Deputy Director). The IAU provides a fixed amount of €70,000 per year, plus the salary and associated costs of a part time fundraiser employed by the IAU. In addition the IAU funds the annual call for proposals (€120,000 per year). Since 2016, these project grants have been paid directly from the IAU in Paris. The total allocation for 2023 projects was €124,011, with the extra €4,011 coming from unspent contingency funds from previous years.

INCOME: For the 2022-2023 financial year, the DSI/NRF provided R4,107,000 and the IAU provided R1,351,888 (total core income of R5,458,888). There was also a carryover of R361,391 coming into the year but all funds were fully utilised by the end of the year.

EXPENDITURE: The 2022-2023 financial year had large costs associated with subsistence and travel due to the IAU General Assembly in Busan and travel opening up in general after the pandemic. The largest expenses for the financial year were staff expenses including salaries, fellows, consultants, recruitment and training (R2,953,627) and special project funding for flagships (R1,130,058). There has been a steady increase, since the pandemic, in office expenses (R182,526) and workshops/conferences (R198,072) due to greater in-person activity. Costs for production, printing and distribution of materials were slightly higher than usual (R275,228) due to large events like the IAU General Assembly in Busan in August 2022.

- IAU (€70,000 p.a.)
- DSI (R1.5m + 6% p.a. plus R1m staffing)
- Other income (projects and postdoc grants)
- Carryover of operating expenses
- IAU Project funding (€124,011)

- Staff expenses (salaries, fellows, consultants, recruitment, training)
- Office expenses (infrastructure and running costs)
- Subsistence and Travel
- Workshops and conferences
- Production, printing and distribution of materials
- OAD Special Projects (Flagships and postdoc grants)
- IAU Project Grants (€124,011)

science & innovation

Department:
Science and Innovation
REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

SAAO

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